

MII.COM: A FINANCIAL SERVICE INNOVATION TO STRENGTHENING CAPITAL AND DEVELOPMENT OF SMES

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Abstract

Micro Small and Medium Enterprises become a sector that is proven to be resistant to the monetary crisis that hit Indonesia in 1997. This business sector controls 99.9 percent of business units in Indonesia and involves thousands of workers in the production process. MSMEs are able to support the national economy. However, the problems faced by UMKM include capital. Capital becomes an important aspect OF the sustainability of business processes. Amid the current industrial revolution 4.0, MSME capital provision still relies on the formal banking sector. On the other hand, for SMEs who are not facilitated by informal or bankable banks get capital through friend loans and debt collectors. From the banking sector, MSME credit in December 2017 was 990,377.6 million rupiahs, while non-MSME loans in the same month amounted to 3,893,426.1 million rupiahs. Social phenomena related to this problem need to be a concern that must be resolved together. Armed with business creativity and innovation, making social phenomena in the community can be used as a solution that has a different perspective in solving the problem. For this reason, an alternative capital provision is needed that can accommodate business needs. Micro Islamic Index (MII.com). This study aims to overcome every problem found in MSMEs. The method used is descriptive qualitative and uses secondary data.

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I. INTRODUCTION

In line with global economic movements, in an effort to increase Indonesia's economic growth, the government issued a series of policy packages that boosted the performance of the entire stock market. The progress of capital markets in a country is used as a benchmark to see the excitement or development of business dynamics in a country that can provide added value to income. This was seen when Dana Mutual Investment Management launched the Jakarta Islamic Index (JII) on July 3, 2000, supported by a fatwa on the sharia capital market on April 18, 2001 by the National Sharia Board of the Indonesian Ulema Council (DSN - MUI) (Mansur, DP, et al, 2016), as well as Islamic bonds effective starting October 30, 2002 (Dewi, A., 2014).

With the emergence of the Islamic stock market is the key to reducing the risk of uncertainty in the conventional capital market and also reduce financial scandals in the international capital market. Not only that, the sharia stock market accommodates people (Muslims and non-Muslims) in their activities to obtain profits and risks, improve the performance, performance, and sustainability of companies included in the Islamic stock exchange in accordance with stock prices, and reduce the occurrence of speculation in the capital market (Komariah , N., 2014).

Meanwhile, the Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) Sector is one of the business sectors that has great potential in Indonesia and is the backbone of the nation's economy. During the crisis in 1998, MSMEs were able to survive amid economic turmoil. Based on the results of data acquisition from Core Indonesia until 2016 UMKM has absorbed 96.7 percent of

the Indonesian workforce. (katadata.co.id). The role of MSMEs is so great, unfortunately, it has not been able to improve economic competitiveness at the international level. This happened due to a lack of access to finance and capital for MSMEs. In addition, banks are not looking at MSMEs in providing financing. Besides bank requirements that are too complicated, interest rates are still high, limited access to MSMEs on information services, as well as lack of guidance, especially in financial management, are the constraints faced by MSMEs in an effort to meet their capital needs (Wardani and Pramono, 2016: Zakiatuzzahra, 2016). From the explanation above we provide a solution as well as a new innovation based on Financial Technology, in an effort to develop MSMEs in Indonesia in overcoming problems and capital as well as good financial management so that MSME activists can compete internationally, namely (MII.com) Micro Islamic Index as FINANCIAL SERVICES INNOVATION AND STRATEGY FOR STRENGTHENING CAPITAL AND DEVELOPMENT OF UMKM.

1.2 Problem Formulation

Based on the background above, the main problems in this study are as follows:

1. How is the role of the Micro Islamic Index mechanism as a micro-based sharia stock market as a new innovative financial service that is effective for the development of MSMEs in the creative industry in Indonesia and is also able to become a secure microstock market for an investor?.
2. How is the urgency of the Micro Islamic Index in improving economic inequality

1.3 The objectives of this study are as follows:

1. Knowing the role of the Micro Islamic Index mechanism as a micro-based Islamic stock market as a new innovative financial service that is effective for the development of MSMEs in the creative industry in Indonesia and is also able to become a microstock market that is safe for investors.
2. Knowing The Urgency of Creative Industry Development to Reduce the Level of Inequality in Indonesia by Utilizing the Investment Fund of Syari'ah Shares Through the Micro Islamic Index Stock Market (MII.com).

1.4 Benefits of Research

The expected benefits of this study are as follows:

1. OJK and JII can make this research as a reference in creating micro-based financial services in the renewable sharia stock market for the development of MSME business players.
2. The government can consider this research as a reference in making policies and synergizing in the development of MSMEs which can then help people improve the level of the economy and reduce economic inequality in Indonesia.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1 Definition of the Stock Exchange

The capital market is a financial market for long-term funds and is a concrete market. The capital market in a narrow sense is a place in an organized physical sense where trading effects are called the stock exchange. Understanding the stock exchange (stock exchange) is an organized system that brings together sellers and buyers of securities that are carried out directly or indirectly. Definition of securities is any securities (securities) issued by a company, for examples: a letter of debt, commercial paper, shares, bonds, proof of the debt, proof of rights (right issue), and a warrant.

2.1.2 Sharia Capital Market

Sharia Capital Market is a capital market activity that has special characteristics. Formed from the fulfillment of sharia principles in creating products, making contracts in the issuance of sharia securities, conducting trade transactions, and conducting other capital market activities. The principles that have to be fulfilled include the avoidance of sharia capital market activities from the elements of persuasion (maysir), uncertainty (gharar), interest system (usury), and uncertainty.

2.1.1 Sharia Capital market products

- Sharia mutual funds
- State Sukk
- Sharia Shares
- Corporate Sukuk

2.2.1 Investment

Simple investment can be interpreted as an activity that aims to develop the property. Investment or investment is one of the teachings of the Islamic concept that fulfills the process of tadrij and trichotomy of knowledge. It can be proved that the concept of investment in addition to knowledge also has a spiritual nuance because it uses sharia norms, as well as being the essence of knowledge and charity. Therefore, investment is highly recommended for every Muslim. By investing can prepare a strong generation, both intellectual, physical and faith aspects so that a whole personality is formed with capacity: (1) have the correct faith; (2) worship in the right way; (3) having noble character; (4) adequate intelligence; (5) able to work / independently; (6) discipline over time; (7) useful for others.

UMKM

The business criteria included in Micro and Small and Medium Enterprises are regulated under the legal umbrella. Based on Law Number 20 of 2008 concerning Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) there are several criteria used to define the definition and criteria for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises.

a. Criteria for Micro, Small and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs)

According to Law Number 20 of 2008 is classified based on the number of assets and turnover owned by a business:

1. Max Micro Business. 50 Million Max. 300 million
2. Small Businesses > 50 Million - 500 Million > 300 Million - 2.5 Billion
3. Medium Enterprises > 500 Million - 10 Billion > 2.5 Billion - 50 Billion

Source: Ministry of Cooperatives and Small and Medium Enterprises, 2012

b. Criteria for Small and Medium Enterprises Based on Development

Based on the Act, from the point of view of its development Rahmana (2008) classify MSMEs in several criteria, namely:

1. Livelihood Activities,
2. Micro Enterprise,
3. Small Dynamic Enterprise,
4. Fast Moving Enterprise.

2.3 Theory of Financial Technology

2.3.1 Definition of Financial Technology

Financial technology comes from the term financial technology or financial technology. According to The National Digital Research Center (NDRC), FinTech is an innovation in the financial sector. Of course, this financial innovation gets a touch of modern technology. In Indonesia, the development of Financial Technology is relatively new with a limited penetration rate in the community. The OJK RI data states that the number of financial providers in Indonesia

has increased threefold than before. If in the first three months of 2016 only 51 Financial Technology companies were operating, it was shot to 135 companies at the end of 2016. (Indonesian Accounting Association, 2017).

3. DATA ANALYSIS

Data analysis techniques used descriptive qualitative patterns. Qualitative descriptive is a data processing of a particular behavior, phenomenon, event, problem, or situation that is the object of the investigation whose findings are in the form of a description of meaningful sentences that explain a particular understanding (Leksono, 2013). The selection of this approach is expected to provide a careful description of the particular situation or symptoms in the object of study. The type of data used in writing scientific papers and used as a reference in making investment fund financing schemes is secondary data. Secondary data obtained from various credible sources include printed books, journals, and articles, official local and foreign websites which are then identified, analyzed. Writing in his research uses data collection techniques in the form of library studies (library research)

4. DISCUSSION

What is the role of the Micro Islamic Index (MII.com) mechanism in the micro-based sharia stock market as an effective new innovative financial service for the development of creative industries in Indonesia. The economy is increasingly global. The era of industrial revolution 4.0 with the characteristics of the internet of things namely the involvement of the internet in all elements of supporting life has become a new phenomenon in society. Starting from online transactions, online transportation, to shipping goods online can be done via the internet. Likewise, the growing investment needs and increasingly complicated capital problems faced by businesses. With the development of technological advancements and investment needs, MII.com seeks to create financial technology-based financial institutions that are better able to meet the needs of society in investing and solving capital problems for MSME business players that will become innovations in the financial sector by creating an online micro sharia stock exchange for UMKM. This application can be accessed easily through smartphones, laptops, and computers. This application is able to provide convenience in online stock transactions, in which there are several features including Login, Home, Trading, Consultation, Information, and Financial Reports. Figure 4.2 Buying and selling schemes for investment in business shares using (MII.com) based on financial technology. Urgency of Creative Industry Development to Reduce the Level of Inequality in Indonesia by Utilizing the Investment Fund of Syari'ah Shares Through the Micro Islamic Index (MII.com) Stock Market. Capital needs for businesses become very important to ensure the sustainability of business processes. Based on data compiled by Bank Indonesia in three consecutive years, business loans are more channeled to non-MSME sectors. In December 2015 UMKM credit was 830,656.2 million rupiahs, while at the same time in-UMKM credit was 3,345,787.1 million rupiah. Whereas UMKM plays a very important role in the stability of the economy which controls almost 99.9 percent of business units in Indonesia. However, from the proportion of capital and operating results, MSMEs are still inferior to the large business sector. In this case, to reduce the level of inequality experienced by MSME activists in the development of the Indonesian economy, the role of investors is needed which can be a support for the nation's economy. Investment in Islamic economics is different from non-Muslim economic investment. In Islam, Islamic entrepreneurs do not use interest rates in calculating investments. Because money interest is usury and can give a lot of negative effects for many people. This is one reason why interest rates are prohibited by the Qur'an. Islam views investment as a mandatory thing to do so that property becomes productive and can be more beneficial for others, and Islam strictly prohibits the hoarding of property.

Allah SWT says :

الدَّهَبَ كُنُزُونَ وَالَّذِينَ اتَّخَذُوا الْأَمْوَالَ الْأَنْبِيَاءَ بِطُلُوعِ النَّاسِ بِالْبَاطِلِ وَالرُّهْبَانِ الْأَخْبَارِ مِنْ كَثِيرٍ إِنْ آمَنُوا الَّذِينَ آتَيْهَا يَا لَوْ وَالْفِئْتَةَ

أَلِيمٌ بِعَذَابٍ قَبِيْثٍ هُمْ فِي سَبِيلِ اللَّهِ فِي يُنْفِقُوْنَهَا

Mean: On the day the silver gold was heated in Hell, then burned with their foreheads, their stomach and back (they said) to them: "This is your treasure that you keep for yourself, so feel now what you save it. " (At-Tawba: 34).

On this basis, financial instruments that are based on shariah principles are needed to bridge the amount of interest of Muslims in Indonesia for halal investment products.

Figure 1. Statistics of Sharia Stocks, OJK * as of November 2015, Data Source: OJK, 2015

Based on the data above shows that the development of Islamic stocks has increased interest from year to year. Seeing the proportion of Islamic stocks that are always experiencing a very rapid increase is a signal that the interest in interest and awareness of the importance of investing in Islamic stocks began to be loved by the people of Indonesia. as a source of business capital income for economic entrepreneurs.

5. CONCLUSION

The concept of developing MSMEs in Indonesia's creative industry can be accelerated by using the role of the Mikro Islamic Index and Syariah stock investment funds to then be channeled to the Creative industry MSME sector. The empowerment program starts from the distribution of stock investment funds through the MII.com website which functions as a medium for collecting investment funds, transparency media for investors and managerial financial reporting education media. Investment funds collected are intended to purchase production machines and fixed assets that support the development of creative industries in Indonesia. In addition, business financial reporting assistance is carried out by the Micro Islamic Index to increase the productivity and professionalism of the development of its business. So that creative industry entrepreneurs can be more independently developed and able to reduce the level of social inequality in Indonesia. The

use of Syari'ah stock investment in the Micro Islamic Index through the MII.com website requires government regulation to regulate the financial technology system that is run. In addition, the government also needs to provide supporting facilities and assistance in socializing the use of stock funds for the productive sector to the public. Openness to research must continue to be improved for the development of stock investment funds for creative industry MSMEs.

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FACTORS AFFECTING BRAND EQUITY: A STUDY IN PROPERTY ADVERTISING

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Abstract

The purpose of this study is to determine the factors that affect brand equity. Some previous studies explain that these factors are television advertising, advertising awareness, brand loyalty, brand image and brand awareness. This study used hypothesis testing methodology. The data was obtained from questionnaire of which the number of variables was 6 items, the number of indicators was 23 items, and the number of respondents selected was 150 people. This empirical study used Structural Equation Modeling (SEM) for the data analysis. The findings in this study were in line with some previous studies.

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1. Introduction

Television has a larger viewer potential. Almost no cost incurred by someone to watch television. Therefore, in general, Indonesian television viewers tend to choose to consume television media, compared to other media. Indonesian population of more than two hundred million people with the population in the regions able to afford viewing television reached 175.296. This figure is certainly a good land for producers to promote their products through television. Television is often considered to be a promotional medium that produces a strong influence on the target. Compared to other promotional media such as newspapers, magazines or radio. Television is the most effective medium to convey information or commercial messages in terms of one of its advantages, namely its ability in reaching a very broad target audience. In addition, television is also capable of generating a very strong impact on consumers through a combination of motion pictures and sound. Brand Equity is one of the most important concepts in the science of marketing, and has been recognized as one of the most valuable intangible assets by most companies (Erenkol and Duygun, 2010). Brand equity is additional utility and value with products or services by brand name (Marinova et al, 2011). High brand equity can cause customers to give positive or strong associations; acquire or increase their cash flow for business, and make product differentiation leading to competitive advantage (Marinova et al, 2011).

Through advertising, the company as a communicator convey a message to the communicant either a message about a product, usefulness, or other important information. One of the fastest growing advertising media is television. The object of the study in this study is METRO TV which is the first 24 hours news television in Indonesia. METRO TV consists of 70% of the news, which is aired in 3 languages, namely Indonesia, English, and Mandarin, plus 30% non educative news programs. METRO TV can be terrestrially captured in 280 cities spread in Indonesian homeland which is transmitted from 52 transmissions. To test the variables affecting brand equity and variables influenced by the brand equity of a product, then the study conducted with sample of a private television viewer in Indonesia. The study was conducted in 2017.

The results of this study is expected to be a material thought to add insight into the Advertising, especially for electronic media advertising such as television advertising. In addition, advertisers are expected to have a reference in making the right decision and effective in order to introduce the product to the target to strengthen the brand.

2. Literature Review

Advertising Television can create long-term brand image for the product (service) or trigger quick sales (Keller, 2016). As a result, based on past study (Huang and Sarigöllü, 2011), it is argued that, advertising can create and improve brand identity by exposing the brand to customers, as well as reinforcing the possibility of being included in the consumer mindset, thus improving the brand's performance. Based on the opinions above, hypotheses are made as follows:

H1 : There is a positive influence of television advertising on brand loyalty.

H2 : There is a positive influence of television advertising on brand awareness.

H3 : There is a positive influence of television advertising on brand equity.

Advertising awareness learns the concept of how consumers engage the website and can improve the effectiveness of advertising. For brands, Keller (2016) define advertising as a form of payment for non-personal presentations and the promotion of ideas, goods or services through mass media such as newspapers, magazines, television or radio by identified sponsors. Based on the opinions above, hypotheses are made as follows:

H4 : There is a positive influence of advertising awareness on brand awareness.

H5 : There is a positive influence of advertising awareness on brand image.

H6 : There is a positive influence of advertising awareness on brand equity.

Brand loyalty differs from other brand equity dimensions, as it is related to usage experience (Salelaw et al, 2015). In addition, brand loyalty reduces uncertainty as well as saves the cost of seeking new relational exchanges with other brands (Erenkol and Duygun, 2010). Brand loyalty makes consumers buy brands regularly and refuse to switch to other competing brands. As a result, brand loyalty is a concept that emphasizes the company, as it can create or retain long-term customer patrons (Marshall, 2015), thereby increasing brand equity. Based on the opinion, hypothesis is made as follows:

H7 : There is a positive influence of brand loyalty on brand equity.

Brand awareness influences consumers in decision making in various ways. When consumers recognize a particular brand, they tend to include names that are on their personal consideration set (Salelaw et al., 2015). It helps consumers to understand the products or services belonging to certain brand categories and what products and services are sold under the brand name (De Matos and Rossi, 2008). Therefore, marketers should concentrate on the right brand management and tactics to build and retain customers by improving relationships between products and customers, thereby affecting the choice of brand customers (Xu and Chen, 2010). Based on the opinions above, hypotheses are made as follows:

H8 : There is a positive influence of brand awareness on brand equity.

H9 : There is a positive influence of brand awareness on brand image.

It is a concept created by consumers for their subjective reasons and personal emotions. The definition of Tjiptono (2015) states that the brand image is the decryption of association and consumer confidence in a particular brand. Alhaddad (2015) define brand image as a set of beliefs possessed about a particular brand. In this case, Confidence plays an important role in the buying decision process when the customer evaluates the selected brand alternatives. Keller in Wu et al.

(2011) defines the image as the total value of the existing societal elements in memoricons that lead to brand perceptions.

H10 : There is a positive influence of brand image on brand equity.

3. Methods

All variables in this study have been tested by using the validity test and reliability test. A description of the validity test and reliability test of this study can be shown in Table 1 below:

Table 1. Validity and Reliability Test.

Variable	Validity Test				Reliability Test		
	N	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	r-tabel	Decision	Item/Statement	Cronbach's Alpha	Decision
Advertising Awareness	150	0,500 – 0,500	0,500	Valid	2	0,926	Reliable
Television Advertising	150	0,588 – 0,692	0,500	Valid	4	0,778	Reliable
Brand Awareness	150	0,796 – 0,909	0,500	Valid	4	0,905	Reliable
Brand Image	150	0,789 – 0,873	0,500	Valid	5	0,919	Reliable
Brand Loyalty	150	0,718 – 0,811	0,500	Valid	4	0,870	Reliable
Brand Equity	150	0,778 – 0,889	0,500	Valid	4	0,852	Reliable

The method used in this study was hypothesis testing, where this method tested the hypotheses, in this case, the effect that occurred in each variable in the hypotheses (Sekaran, 2004). A description of the conceptual model of this study can be shown in Figure 1 below:

Figure 1. Conceptual Model.

This study used SEM (Structural Equation Model) analysis method which was run by using AMOS program (Analysis of Moment Structures) version 21. Path diagram in this study can be seen in Figure 2 below:

Figure 2. Path Diagram.

4. Results

From the results of data processing that has been done on the variables in this study, namely television advertising, advertising awareness, brand loyalty, brand image, brand awareness of brand equity in Property ads on Metro TV, it can be known the SEM model estimation results, shown in the Table 2 below:

Table 2. Estimation Result of SEM Model.

Hypotheses	Relationship	Estimate	C.R.	P-value	Conclusion
H1	Television Advertising → Brand Loyalty	0.253	1,878	0,060	Was not supported
H2	Television Advertising → Brand Awareness	0.496	4,433	0,000	Was supported
H3	Television Advertising → Brand Equity	0,223	2,021	0,043	Was supported
H4	Advertising Awareness → Brand Awareness	0,121	2,051	0,040	Was supported
H5	Advertising Awareness → Brand Image	0,479	7,287	0,000	Was supported
H6	Advertising Awareness → Brand Equity	0,189	2,027	0,043	Was supported
H7	Brand Loyalty → Brand Equity	0,238	2,005	0,045	Was supported
H8	Brand Awareness → Brand Equity	0,315	4,094	0,000	Was supported

H9	Brand Awareness	→ Brand Image	0,276	2,015	0,044	Was supported
H10	Brand Image	→ Brand Equity	0,121	2,051	0,040	Was supported

5. Discussion

The results of study on H1 show that television advertising does not increase brand loyalty. This happens because the television advertising offered is not attractive, or people will still buy even without the television advertising. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Salelaw et al. (2015) which in his study concluded that there is no significant influence between television advertising against brand loyalty.

The results of study on H2 support the results of study that has been done by Salelaw et al. (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between television advertising and brand awareness.

The results of study on H3 show that television advertising will increase equity to a brand. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Zohoori (2013) where in his study concluded that there is significant influence between television advertising and brand equity.

The result of the study on H4 shows that the advertising awareness will increase brand awareness. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between advertising awareness and brand awareness.

The results of the study on H5 show that brand awareness helps to improve the image of a brand. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand awareness and brand image.

Results of study on H6 indicate that advertising awareness will increase brand equity. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between advertising awareness and brand equity.

The results of study on H7 indicate that brand loyalty will increase brand equity. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand loyalty and brand equity.

The results of study on H8 show that brand awareness will increase the equity of a brand. The results of this study do not support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand awareness and brand equity.

The results of the study on H9 show that brand awareness will improve the brand image for the product. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand awareness and brand image.

The results of study on H10 show that brand image will increase brand equity for the product. The results of this study support the results of study that has been done by Alhaddad (2015) which in his study concluded that there is a significant influence between brand image and brand equity.

6. Conclusion

Based on the discussion above, we could conclude that factors affecting brand equity in Property Advertising were television advertising, advertising awareness, brand loyalty, brand image and brand awareness. This reinforced some previous studies.

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APPLICATION OF FECES BRIQUETTE FOR ALTERNATIVE ENERGY IN INDONESIA'S VILLAGES

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Abstract

The number of people in the world increase rapidly every day. This condition also make the needs of consumption increase. One of the best way to solve the problem is by increase the number of livestock. According to data from Central Statistics Agency, the number of livestock in Indonesia by 2017 are 2.313.941 heads. Livestock's waste and its by-products supply greenhouse gas emissions at least 32.564 million tons of CO_{2e} per year, or about 51 percent of annual greenhouse gas emissions worldwide. In other place, according from source data in 2016, there are 12.659 villages from total 74.759 villages in Indonesia are still living with no electricity. This study aimed to generalize the electrical activities in Indonesia also to minimize gas emission and environmental pollution produced by livestock's waste (feces). Methods used in this study divided into two steps, feces briquette making and briquette converting into electrical source then measured by calorimeter bomb. The result of this study showed that calories produced from 4 kgs feces briquettes are equally the same with 10,64 kgs coals. As conclusion, instead of using non renewable energy from coal, feces briquette which can be produce everyday is much more efficient for electrical source.

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1. Introduction

The number of people in the world increase rapidly every day. This condition also make the needs of consumption increase. One of the best way to solve the problem is by increase the number of livestock. Unfortunately the management of livestock waste still become a complex environmental issue. Livestock waste can have both positive and negative impact on environment. Most of Indonesian livestock farms still not manage the waste well and left it decomposed itself so the environmental had been polluted too. According to FAO (Food and Agriculture Organization) in 2006, an estimated 7.516 million metric tons per year of CO_{2e} (carbon dioxide equivalent), or 18 percent of annual greenhouse gas emissions caused by cattle, buffalo, sheep, goats, camels, horses, pigs, and poultry. According to the analysis of Goodland and Anhang (2009), livestock and its by-products supply greenhouse gas emissions at least 32.564 million tons of CO_{2e} per year, or about 51 percent of annual greenhouse gas emissions worldwide.

According to data from the Central Statistics Agency, the number of livestock in Indonesia by 2017 are 2.313.941 heads. By that amount, the waste product is certainly not small number. This number surely produce waste that can have the negative impact for environmental if can't be managed well. One of the most popular waste that can be harm human's health is feces, moreover from cattles with polygastric digestion system. This polygastric digestion system convert food into ammonia which can be one of the global warming cause. The price of feces itself is free or sometimes cost as IDR 40,00 or equal as MYR 0,011 per kgs which really cheap. That's why feces can be called as black gold because it is a priceless thing which can be converted into useful product if managed effectively.

Based on these reasons then the government drafted the Law of the Republic of Indonesia Number 32 of 2009 on the Protection and Environmental Management. Chapter 1 Article 1, Verse 3 stating that: “the protection and management of the environment means a systematic and integrated approach to preserve the environment and prevent pollution and/or damage to the environment that includes planning, utilization, control, maintenance, supervision, and law enforcement.”

In other place, according to data from government official source in 2012, Indonesia have 17.504 islands in total. This islands divided into 13.449 islands which already verified, and 4.055 islands which still not officially verified yet. Moreover, according from source data in 2016, there are 12.659 villages from total 74.759 villages in Indonesia which are still living with no electricity. This number of villages without electrical activities are very apprehensive compared to those villages which live near the capital city, mostly in Java island. Most of this villages which already become industrial area are fully supported by electrical activity in all aspects. This unbalance comparison can be manage by the good managing in waste product to produce electrical energy. One of effort is by convert waste (feces) from livestock product into briquette. This briquette are aimed to gain the electricity activities of some small islands in Indonesia. Those islands have to develop too considered by other island (example is Java) which already developed with technology. Another goals are also for minimize the gas emission and environmental pollution produced by livestock’s waste (feces). This paper can give advantage for writers, researchers, governments, and farmers as well in managing waste. Also, for better and more equity Indonesia.

2. Literature review

Feces from the explanation of Daely (2000) is the solid or semisolid metabolic waste from animal’s digestive tract, discharged through the anus or cloaca during a process called defecation. Urine and feces together are called excreta in poultry. Rumen’s content can also be managed as briquette because it content fibers, high protein microorganism, and methan.

Gerber *et al.* (2013) state that livestock sector contribute 14,5 % emission gas in global warming worldwide and 41% of it comes from ruminant’s manure. Hambali (2007) said that 10-30 kgs feces can be produce from a cow per day. Lingga (1991) state that ruminant’s feces content N 0,3%, P 0,2%, K 0,15%, water 80% for cow and N 0,7%, P 0,4%, K 0,25%, and water 64% for goat. Normally, poultry can produce excreta 6,6% from it’s total weight. Poultry’s excreta contents N 1%, P 0,80%, K 0,40% and 55% water.

According to Susana (2007) briquette is an organic material derived from living bodies, both plants and animals, one of the example is manure (feces). The feces can be processed by mix it with starch flour so it can be coagulated and solid. This dough then can be molded. The final product of this molded dough then could be checked by burn it on fire. Time measured of this fire being burn t used as parameters to know if the product can be use effectively as alternative energy.

Briquette commonly used as substitution for Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG). Most of Indonesian use LPG for cooking. Unfortunately, LPG is derived from fossils which include as non renewable energy. That’s why LPG is pricy, so briquette could be one of alternative. Daely (2000) mentioned that 4 kgs feces briquettes are equal with 6 kgs LPG also equal with 144 hours fire on non-stop.

Take a look of this opportunity, instead of using briquette as LPG substitution, this paper trying to convert briquette from feces as electrical source in Indonesia’s no electricity area. The main concept is by using the heat of briquette combustion result as generator mover to produce electricity. Both coal and briquette is utilizing steam from combustion result. But coal which made of fossils can’t be renewable. So, as comparison, BTBRD-BPPT (2017) state that coal compounds calories of 6.322 kcal per kgs. Meanwhile, LPG compounds calories of 11.220 kcal/per kgs. It means that 10,64 kgs coal equal with 6 kgs LPG.

There are 3 methods for converting briquettes into electrical source include gasification, densification, and combustion. The main concept of gasification is utilizing carbon dioxide (CO₂) from burning result as main compounds in moving the generator. Densification is a process which utilizing briquette's pressure as generator mover. Combustion is a process which using calor as main compound to produce electrical source.

3. Materials and methods

3.1. Materials

3.1.1. Equipments. Equipments used for briquette's making are press-machine biobriquette, crusher, stove, weight scale, stop watch, hoe, vessel, mixer, carbonizator, molder and oven. Equipments for electrical source converting are boiler tank, stove, turbine, generator, magnetic field, and condenser.

3.1.2. Ingredients. Ingredients used for briquette's making are livestock's feces, rice husk, coconut shell, and starch flour with comparison of 5:3:2:1 also 5:2:3:2. Ingredients for electrical source converting are end product of feces briquette, fire, and water condenser.

3.2. Methods

3.2.1 Briquette making. Livestock's feces, rice husk, coconut shell, and starch flour measured with comparison of 5:3:2:1 also 5:2:3:2 for total briquettes (600 g) for square mold and 100 g for cylindrical mold. Then, add starch flour which already mixed by water and heat on the vessel. All of those ingredients mixed homogenely. This dough then put in the press-machine biobriquette. The pressure controlled and variated on 200 kgs/cm² and 225 kgs/cm². Pressing process in 5 and 7,5 minutes to make it more solid. After molded, then briquette is being dried with oven with some temperature variated in 50 and 60 °C. The drying process being done in 2 and 3 days.

3.2.2. Electrical source making. Electrical source making divided into four processes. First one is process on producing steam. Boler tank filled with water and heat by primer energy from briquette. Heating process produce steam. Second, convection calor into mechanical energy process. Steam from the heating product, with pressure and temperature measured stream to the turbine. The streams can be used as turbine mover. The turbine's moving convert steam into mechanical energy. Third, mechanical energy convection into electrical energy. Turbine is connected directly into generator. Inside of the generator, there are magnetic coils which produce electrical source which then stream into output generator terminal. Last one, condensation process. By product of steam for moving the turbin go to condenser. Condenser using cold water with big amount to make condensation process more effective. The condenser water then can be used for filling boiler again.

4. Results and discussion

This program will gain the farmer knowledge. Additionally, the raised of public interest and farmers to manage the feeding and livestock waste into products such as biogas, compost, liquid fertilizer and briquettes. Daely (2000) state that test materials for briquette bioarang done thermolysis process (pyrolysis) on biomass briquettes by using retort (heating oven) with heating temperature and a constant holding time, 300°C for 2 hours, and treated with inert gas and non-inert gas treatment. After the process is complete, the retrieval is done, data burning calorific value, and carried on. End of sample testing process using adiabatic bomb calorimeter, where taking data is done 3 times for each test material, and the average value is taken. From the test result is calculated dry calorific value (GEk) and wet calorific value (GEb) biomass briquettes and bioarang briquettes.

Electrical energy source making divided into four processes. First one is process on producing steam by heating. Second, convection calor into mechanical energy process. Third, mechanical energy convection into electrical energy. Fourth, condensation process (GeothermalIndo, 2017). By using this method, electrical energy can be produced from feces briquettes.

According to some literature above, instead of using non renewable energy from coal, feces briquette is much more efficient for electrical source. By using LPG as parameter, 4 kgs feces briquettes are equally the same with 10,64 kgs coals. Most of coals are made of plant's fossils. The process of fossils making it self take million years. Meanwhile, livestock's feces which become the main product of briquette can be produce everyday. These are provements that feces briquette is a good idea for electrical energy source in Indonesia.

Substantially can be achieved by application of briquette's making as electrical source. First, provide training also empower communities and traditional farmers to manage their animal waste, so it can provide more value to the farm business. Second, community and traditional farmers can run production process on the farm effectively and efficien so that the waste from the rest of the uneaten-feed can be reduced. In addition, the farm management has also become the focus of the program that is traditional farms can increase the productivity for major livestock products. Third, this can direct community's minds and farmers to develop their entrepreneurship spirit. The way is by marketing the processed products of animal wastes into products that are environmentally friendly and can be a source of alternative energy for other areas of Indonesia. Fourth, for government to use feces briquette as the renewable electrical energy source and support to develop it nationally so it can be used as for no electrical activities villages in Indonesia. It can increasing equity in all aspects.

There are several elements that involved in the implementation of using feces briquettes as electrical source, such as government, stakeholder, village communities and farmers, also academics. Government's role are providing support and facilities to run the program. In addition, they also can allocated fund and play a role in expanding this program to be run in various region in Indonesia, mostly for no electrical activities villages. Stakeholder, entrepreneurs and companies can have a strategic role to run this program. The company can provide support facilities and infrastructure to facilitate the implementation of programs, especially when processing animal waste in workshop.

Communities and farmers are the object of the program should have an active role. Not all of the people directly involved. People who run the program is not restricted but should have sufficient physical condition and willing to change. People who are not involved can be a contributor to the raw materials for waste treatment voluntarily, such as feces, urine, and the uneaten feed. Also, overseeing the course of the program passively. The intellectuals or academics (involving faculty and students) should be involved in taking this role. Lecturers and students are able to provide socialization, recommendations, training and guidance for communities and farmers or other elements, so the program can be achieved on target.

5. Conclusion and recommendation

5.1. Conclusion

Feces briquette is an idea that arise because of the increasing issue which blame livestock sectors as the main reason of greenhouse effect emissions in the world because of its waste. This inovation is expected as solution to animal waste management which previously thought as priceless products become the efficient renewable energy source. Also, this inovation is a useful activity and give addictive impact to the applicator because involves all the village member (leaders, communities, and farmers) to run the program. This inovationis aim to increase electrical activities in Indonesia equally. This innovation also make be the opportunities to increase the quality of human resources to become the high quality human and capable to compete in recent time even for the future, moreover for better Indonesia. There will be no more left behind area in Indonesia, and equity can be achieved in all aspects.

5.2. Recommendation

- a. Feces briquette needs cooperative work from all elements to become sustain and give benefits.
- b. Feces briquette needs intensive assistance from the academics to run continuously.

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SHIFT IN MEANING OF SEKURA FESTIVAL IN WEST LAMPUNG DISTRICT

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Abstract

The problem raised in this research is the change of people perception towards Sekura festival in West Lampung district. The purpose of this research is to analyze the changes that occur in celebration of Sekura festival in West Lampung district. This research employed a qualitative method and ethnography approach which aimed to reveal the facts and phenomena in the festival which focused on the pattern of activities and traditions of a group. Data were collected by using participant observation method, in-depth interview, and documentation. The data were obtained from the selected informants. The main informants involved performers of Sekura, committees, and Adat leaders, and the supporting informants involved chief of Pekon Balak and his people, Sukarami and Kegeringan people. The data were analyzed by using the Interactive Model of Analysis which covered three component analyses those are data reduction, data presentation, and conclusion in the form of an interactive cycle. The result of the research shows that there are some changes occur in Sekura festival, comprised of 1) the change in process of Sekura festival namely losing of traditional procession, 2) shift in meaning of fashion and attribute in Sekura festival, and 3) shift in meaning of *nyakak buah* (climbing slipper pole game).

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1. Introduction

Lampung is one of the provinces in Indonesia which is located in a strategic location. It is located in the southeastern tip of Sumatra Island. In the northern part, it is directly adjacent to the provinces of South Sumatra and Bengkulu and in the southern part borders of Lampung is directly adjacent to the Sunda Strait. Geographically, Lampung Province is the gateway between two major islands in Indonesia, namely Sumatra and Java. This is reflected in the development of the meaning of the slogan *Sai Bumi Ruwai Jurai* which means "one house with two doors". At first, the meaning of the slogan refers to two indigenous Lampung tribes namely *Sai Batin Lampung Ulun* and *Pepadun Lampung Ulun*. Then, the meaning of the slogan is developing and refers to the indigenous people of Lampung and transmigrants. In the end, *Sai Bumi Ruwai Jurai* refers to the gate of Sumatra and the gate of Java (Sunda Strait, Bakahunei Harbor).

In fact, as a province which is a route for interisland's transportation and trade, Lampung has an increase in cultural diversity. Theory of fungsional culture which proposed by Malinowski¹ stated that culture play the role as means to solve the problems as the effort to adapt with nature in order to supply their needs. The population of Lampung Province is dominated by migrants. The transmigrants consisted of Javanese (61.88%), Sundanese (11.27%) and other tribes (15%).² The transmigrants from outside Lampung brought their cultural customs which contribute to regional cultural diversity. Levi'-Strauss³ declared his oppinion that the inter-culture interaction makes the people's identity stronger in term of culture. The continuity of culture is evoked as cultural change modus. However, the 'new' culture can also threaten the existence of indigenous (local) culture, one of which is the *Sekura* Festival. The development of technology, information, and communication, as well as education, has contributed to the changes in this tradition. The globalization and change of culture become part of society.

Basically, cultures are dynamic and develop, because there is no static culture. Culture changes along with the development of the environment and its people. Change of culture was caused by several factors including 1) changes in the natural environment, 2) contacts between other groups, 3) the existence of discovery, 4) the adoption of elements of other national material cultures, and 5) changes on life's vision.⁴ Those factors affect changes in the people's perception of the meaning of *Sekura* festival both symbolically and practically. Some changes which appear in the *Sekura* festival are in the procession, attributes, dress, and so forth.

2. Research Methodology

This research uses the descriptive qualitative method with the ethnographic approach. This research is intended to reveal facts and phenomena which focus on the activities and traditions of a group. Data collection was carried out by using Participant Observation techniques, interviews, and documentation. Data sources were obtained from key informants and supporting informants. The main informants consisted of *Sekura* performers, the executive committee, and the adat leader and the supporting informants involved the chief of Pekon Balak, the community of Pekak Balak, volunteers, Kegeringan and Cangu, as well as the tourists from outside the West Lampung Regency. Data analysis uses an interactive analysis model consisting of three analytical processes namely data reduction, data presentation, and conclusions in an interactive form cycle.⁵

3. Results and Discussion

The research was carried out in several villages / pekon namely Pekon Balak, Pekon Sukarami, Pekon Kegeringan, and Pekon Cangu, West Lampung Regency. In 2018 there are 12 pekon who carry out this tradition. The study was carried out in the four villages which will represent and describe the *sekura* festival. The results of the study indicate that there are several changes in public perception of the meaning of *Sekura* tradition. *Sekura* Festival is an indigenous tradition of West Lampung people who grows, develops and survives until now. Unfortunately, the *Sekura* Festival has been influenced by the migrants' cultures so that *sekura* performers and the community have a different perception on the meaning of the recent *Sekura* festival and the previous *sekura* festival.

1. *The Change in Procession of Sekura Festival Namely Losing of Traditional Procession (Traditional-Modern)*

Sekura festival emerged around the 7th century. *Sekura* festival means worship for ancestors and nature spirits of Pesagi Mountain. Pesagi Mountain is the highest mountain in Lampung Province and it is a source of livelihood for the surrounding communities through hunting and farming at the foot of the mountain. People assume that everything used and consumes comes from nature. When Islam came to West Lampung and animism was abandoned, *Sekura* Festival was not be held.⁶ *Sekura* Festival is held again on Eid al-Fitr as a celebration of victory and the party as of ngejalang (forgive each other).

Based on research of Mustika (2011)⁶, Thomas (2014)², and Fauzan (2016)⁷, the implementation of the *Sekura* festival is began with traditional music show, singing show, kasidah (song for praising God and Prophet Muhammad), menyambai (declamation), welcoming speech by chief of adat and village elders, quatrain correspondence and pencak silat (Indonesian martial art). Then, the host gave instruction to shake hands and prayer as the last. The series of opening events for each village / pekon are different from each other in accordance with their respective policies. While the core program in this tradition is the same namely performing parade around the village, and Nyakak Buah (climbing slippery pole game)

However, regrettably, in the last few years in the research area, the implementation of the *Sekura* festival has undergone a change. The implementation procedure is no longer includes traditional activities as stated earlier. The use of traditional music and *menyambai* has begun to be abandoned and changed using modern music and songs such as electric music show. Meanwhile, traditional activities which carrying out local wisdom are transformed into more fun and lively activities such as race and other activities. Thus, the sacred and traditional atmosphere becomes less felt in the implementation of this tradition. Pekon Balak and Pekon Sukarami accomplished the opening ceremony with a welcoming speech from Pangeran (Chief of custom) and several competitions, such as the *Sekura* costume competition with two categories, *Sekura Kamak* and *Sekura Betik / Helau* with an age range of 4-13 years old. The winners of this competition are participants with the worst costumes for *Sekura Kamak* and the most beautiful costumes for *Sekura Betik/Helau*. In addition, there are also *kasidah* competitions, *menyambai* competition, and declamation.

2. *Shift in Meaning of Fashion and Attributes in Sekura Festival (Masks and Costume)*

Sekura or called *Sekukha* in the Lampung language means covering the face. Covering all parts of the face with something like a mask, cloth, or makeup is the main requirement to join this tradition. However, for costume and other attributes are adjusted to the type of *Sekura* played by the *Sekura* participants. First, *Sekura Kamak* uses a wood mask with human and animal characters to cover face and wear a bad costume. It means that the *Sekura Kamak* participants wear dirty clothes which used for hunting or going to the farm, ragged, and used dried leaves as the embellishment. This is interpreted as symbols that humans are part of nature, live from natural products and live in nature. It is also the form of gratitude to nature. *Sekura Kamak* is used by married men. It means that married men are considered as strong people which is strong in taking care of their family and when climbing slippery pole game (*Nyakak Buah*). They can also work together and it is considered as a solid foundation in the community.

Second, *Sekura Helau / Betik* is known as *Sekura Cantik / Bagus*. The type of costume wore by the participants is neat, nice and beautiful. The characteristic of this *sekura* is the use of colourful material to cover their face and is played by unmarried men. This is interpreted as the charm and beauty of girls. Because *Sekura* is only played and performed by men, the costume wore by the participants is representative of girls in the *Sekura* performers' family. When a family has a daughter, the *Sekura* performer uses one long cloth and is equipped with a shawl. Moreover, if a family have five daughters, the *Sekura* performers will wear five different long cloths.

In fact, people's perceptions experienced a shift in the meaning of *Sekura's* attributes of the costume. *Sekura Kamak* is no longer only wore by adult men but also wore by teenagers and even children. They do not know the meaning of *Sekura Kamak* (mask) that they use to cover their face. The reason why they chose to use *Sekura Kamak* is that the costume is easy to get especially the *Sekura Ngandung* which is the symbol of a pregnant woman. The children covered their faces with masks both from wood and cloth, wearing negligee clothes and backpacks as their distended bellies. The real shift in the meaning occurs at *Sekura Helau / Betik*. Colourful clothes wore are no longer represent girls in a family but are valued as aesthetic and beauty. The *Sekura* performers are no longer pay attention to the amount of cloth used to decorate themselves as the representative of his sister. This means that the *sekura* performers are no longer pay attention to the meaning of the *sekura* or mask used.

The shift in the meaning of *Sekura* is not only the use of *Sekura* (masks) but also the use of costume and attributes. Some shifts in costume are the use of costume that is considered impolite, such as wearing clothes that shown too much part of the participants' body, wearing an underwear

outside clothes, wearing short pants and more. Some Sekura Kamak performances cut off the tree more than one each person. They cut off trees in the people's agricultural field. After finishing the festival, they left the trees on the side of street, and it causes a mess. However, the sekura participants still maintain to completely cover their faces by using a mask which is the soul of Sekura festival. Moreover, in the *sekura* festival, costume and attributes are complement aspect.

Sekura festival in 2018 is dominated by *Sekura Kamak* while *Sekura Betik / Helau* is not widely used by teenagers and singles (age range 14-20s). However, there are also interesting sights in Pekon Balak, Sukarami, and Canggus, many children who aged 2-5 years old join the festival using *Sekura Betik/Helau* and dress up very nicely and beautifully. Moreover, their parents are deliberately prepared *Sekura's* costume which is decorated with charming and beautiful attributes. In the end, the *Sekura* Festival is a celebration of the people so that everyone can express their feeling according to their wishes. The main concern of this festival is to completely cover the face so that *Sekura* participants will not be recognized by tourists and visitors.

Figur 1. *Sekura Betik/Helau*.

Source: Researchers documentation.

Figur 2. *Sekura Kamak*

Source: Researchers documentation.

3. *Shift in Meaning of Nyakak Buah (Climbing Slippery Pole Game)*

Sekura festival has a core event called Nyakak Buah (climbing a slippery pole game). Nyakak Buah means taking fruit. There is a pole that is considered as the symbol of a tree and at its peak, there are various kinds of items (gifts) which are considered as the symbol of fruits. Nyakak Buah has several meanings, namely mutual cooperation and living together harmoniously. This can be seen in Nyakak Buah activity in which a group consisting of several men likened to a society. They formulate strategies together and unite forces to raise a trusted member to the top and take fruit or gifts. However, all the gifts obtained will be distributed equally to all group members. The meaning of Nyakak Buah is that a large society must help one another and unite in reaching a goal for the benefit of all (all group members). Nyakak Buah is also carried out by married men. It means that they are ready to enter the community and can be trusted to hold a responsibility.

In fact, in the last ten years, people's perceptions began to shift in interpreting Nyakak Buah. Nyakak Buah is still carried out in groups with an age range of 30-45 years old or married men. There are only a few things that change between them. Members no longer give their shoulders and collaborate to raise their members to the top. Instead, one of the group members is believed to climb the pole using a rope to the top. The recent nyakak buah use tool which previous nyakak buah did not use tools.

Adults *Sekura* participants have their own perception. The *sekura* participants with more than 50 years old interpreted *Sekura* as a tradition that was very meaningful and integrated with them. For example Ajong Ri (75 years old) and Ajong Danang (70 years old), both are the oldest *Sekura*

participants in Pekon Balak. He interpreted *Sekura* as himself. *Sekura* tradition, society, people and nature are an inseparable entity. Both participants use *Sekura* Kamak Ngandung and always follow the *Sekura* tradition every year, even though they only take part in the parade and do not participate in the Nyakak Buah activities. For *Sekura* participants like them, this tradition has changed a lot including the procession and the show. In the past, there will be more *sekura* participants than the visitors, even women will feel afraid to approach and shake hands with the *Sekura* participants. However, nowadays, there will be more visitors and merchants selling merchandise, this phenomenon is called as "Pasar Pindah" by the surrounding community.

Conclusion

Public perception in interpreting *sekura* festival has begun to shift. The community no longer carries out the traditionality of *Sekura* festival. It means that the meaning of some activities is transformed from tradition to more modern and enjoyable activities. Thus, the sacredness and deity are no longer felt. The young *sekura* participants with the age range of 4-13 years old actually do not know what the meaning of the mask they play and the dress/attributes they wear. The teenage *sekura* participants (14-20 years old) using *Sekura* Betik / Helau no longer interpreted the cover clothes as a representative of their female colleagues at home but interpreted it as an art and beauty. However, the adults *sekura* participants (30-75 years old), in fact, there is no age limitation to join this tradition, have different perceptions in interpreting this tradition. Thus, the most important thing is that the community continues to maintain and preserve this festival as a local wisdom of the people of West Lampung.

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ANNUAL MANDATORY MONEY TARIFF CHANGE IN BATAM: POLITICAL ECONOMY REVIEW

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Abstract

Annual mandatory money is land lease cost that must be paid by user of land allocation in Batam Island to Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA). BIFZA changes annual mandatory money tariff through BIFZA Head Regulation Number 19 of 2016. It makes problems that are [1] Rejection of community elements; [2] Sluggishness of economic growth; [3] Incoordination with outside stakeholders; and [4] Disadvantage threat to workers. This research objectives, first, identify and explain reason of annual mandatory money tariff change. Second, it identifies and explains advantage and disadvantage of annual mandatory money tariff change. This research uses rational choice theory and public choice theory which are from new political economy school as a theoretical frameworks. Approach is used by qualitative with descriptive analysis methods. Data is collected by interview and documentation study. Data was collected for it is analyzed by process of reduction, presentation, and verification. Research result concluded that, first, reason of annual mandatory money tariff change is caused by unilateral action from BIFZA that changes it by outside stakeholders incoordination. Second, advantage and disadvantage of annual mandatory money tariff change show that advantage side is BIFZA and foreign investor. While, disadvantage side is community, businessman, and worker.

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1. Introduction

Annual mandatory money is land lease cost that must be paid by user of land allocation in Batam Island who is characterized by individual, investor, or legal entity to Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA). Income of annual mandatory money is used by BIFZA as development of in infrastructure and public facilities so Batam can be said a city of very rapid in business climate growth city in Indonesia [1]. Annual mandatory money payment is paid every 30 years for the first time, and it is next every 20 years forever. All of land in Batam Island can only be leased through annual mandatory money tariff because the land is owned by the state. The authority for land management rights had been given by Central Government to Batam Island Industrial Area Development Authority which based at Presidential Decree Number 41 of 1973 and it has delegated to BIFZA (new name from Batam Island Industrial Area Development Authority) which based at Government Regulation Number 46 of 2007 [2 p23]. The status of land in Batam Island can only be in the form of business rights, building rights, and used rights which based at Government Regulation Number 40 of 1996.

BIFZA changes annual mandatory money tariff that based at BIFZA Head Regulation Number 19 of 2016. The comparison between old and new annual mandatory money tariff is increased from range of 151,7% to 2640,4% to all allocations that are housing, commercial, industrial, tourism, cultivation area, and public facilities. It makes problems that are *first*, rejection of community elements. The rejection was carried out by *Melayu Melawan* at 2 November 2016 [3], businessmen at 2 November 2016 [4], workers at 9-10 November 2016 [5], *Gerakan Rakyat Melawan UWTO* at 14-16 November 2016 [6], Regional House of Representatives of Batam City

at 14 October 2016 [7], and Batam City Government at 25 October 2016 [8]. *Second*, sluggishness of economic growth. Batam's economic growth in 2016 numbered to 5.45% is slowing that compared to growth in 2015 that numbered to 6.83% [9 p55]. *Third*, incoordination with outside stakeholders. A member of the Batam Area Council, Jumaga Nadeak admitted that he refused annual mandatory money tariff change [10] because other than businessmen disadvantage and the discussion did not involve Batam Area Council. *Fourth*, disadvantage threat to workers. Chair of All Indonesian Workers Union of Kepulauan Riau Province, Syaiful Badri said that annual mandatory money tariff change would add burden to workers because the workers and investment world could not be separated [5].

1. 1. Objective

Based on the research question identified earlier, so objectives, first, identify and explain reason of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016. Second, it identifies and explains advantage and disadvantage of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016.

2. Theoretical Framework

Political economy is understood to analyze political processes in relation with economy or it is the systematic study of about the relationship between economic process and political process [11]. This research uses rational choice theory and public choice theory which are from new political economy school as a theoretical frameworks.

2. 1. Rational Choice Theory

According to Deliarnov [12 p134] in general, rationality developed by new political economy experts, especially in rational choices, is related to concepts such as preference, beliefs, opportunities, and action. To be more easily understood, example we are faced by two choices, namely A and B. Three ways to express preferences between the two choices are (1) A is better than B (notated with $A > B$); (2) B is better than A (notated with $B > A$ or $A < B$); and (3) A is as good as (or as bad as) B (notated with $A=B$). If you were ranking $A > B$ and $B > C$, based on theory of revealed preference and according to transitivity axiom, the conclusions are $A > C$. The concept of rational choice can be applied to the government as an actor or to individual voters in elections because the criteria used are same, and opportunities considered comparable. For new political economy experts, the important is that rational choices can be carried out, either by individuals or by the government. They do not reject the framework of political existence, but they assume that political behavior and political institutions can be analyzed as well as economic behavior and market institutions.

2. 2. Public Choice Theory

James Buchanan [13 p70] reviewed it from two separate aspects which are two main elements from a public choice perspective. The first aspect is the exchange aspect (*catallactics*). If you use *catallactics* in more deeply, then this perspective can succeed in bringing the definition of spontaneous and complex order into a simple concept of exchange. This complex exchange is a process of contractual agreement that can be given more meaning than just the exchange of two people who make transactions. If economics can explain market phenomena, namely meetings between seller and buyer, then new political economy can also explain the concept of political markets. Market in the economics are governed by basic laws, namely spontaneous order. Meanwhile, the political market is used as a concept to explain the exchange between political parties and voters and between the government in power and people. The foundation of the political market is the game rules of constitutional and democratic, not on the basis of power.

While, the second aspect is a postulation, known as economical human (*homo economicus*). It is used to explain the inclusive public choice perspective. The true meaning of this concept is that humans tend to maximize utility benefits for themselves because they are faced

with the reality of limited resources their have. Everyone experiences a problem of scarcity of resources so the concept of *homo economicus* automatically explains the consequences of human behavior on the action or economic satisfaction that it does. All people will have the tendency of *homo economicus*. So, this concept has nothing to do with the nature of capitalism, greed or economical animal. Technically, this concept is described in the utility function where individual continues to strive that fulfills his/her self interest. This nature means very basic so no one individual is free from it (except the abnormal). Self interest is a very human nature that cannot be revoked or arbitrarily restricted by anyone. From this intrinsic meaning, collective model can be built without losing human nature.

3. Method

Approach is used by qualitative with descriptive analysis methods. Qualitative is the emphasis on processes and meanings that are not tested, or measured precisely, in terms of quantity, number, intent, or frequency [14 p14]. This approach try to understand information in description form of phenomena between supplier and demander in responded about problems of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016. For obtaining primary data sources, researcher uses purposive technique to determine informants. By purposive technique, informants were deliberately chosen with certain considerations [15 p318] that are knowing, competent, and involved with the research topic. The informants are Head of Administration Sub-Division of Land Management Office of BIFZA, Deputy Chairman 1 of the All-Indonesia Trade Union Confederation of Batam City, Expert Council Chairman of Local Youth Association of Batam City, Expert Council Chairman of Chamber of Commerce and Industry of Batam City, Vice Chairman of Batam Special All-Indonesia Housing and Settlement Developer Association, Chairperson of Commission 1 of Regional House of Representatives of Batam City, Head of Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency of Batam City, public figures, community, and businessmen. While, the secondary data sources is several documents related.

Data is collected by interview [15 p362] and documentation study [15 p80]. The interview is collecting data by asking questions directly by researcher to informants in Batam. The informant's answers were recorded with a recording device. Meanwhile, documentation study is using documents that have been written from 2016 to understand the phenomena of research. Data was collected for next it is analyzed by process of reduction, presentation, and verification [15 p11]. Reduction is the process of selecting raw data obtained from interview recordings, written records, and other documents when on location. Presentation is the activity of presenting research data in form of processed narrative texts, tables and drawings, and verification is the activity of formulating conclusions based on the two previous activities.

4. Result and Discussion

4. 1. Reason of Annual Mandatory Money Tariff Change

Amount of annual mandatory money tariff is full authority by Head of Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA) with Finance Minister approval which based at Article 59 Government Regulation Number 40 of 1996. It Guideline is regulated at Article 3 Finance Minister Regulation Number 100/PMK.05/2016. Reason of annual mandatory money tariff change that is delivered by BIFZA is *first*, finance minister regulation. Annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 is caused by Finance Minister Regulation Number 148/PMK.05/2016 which replaces Finance Minister Regulation Number 153/PMK. 05/2012. It affects annual mandatory money tariff change that based at BIFZA Head Regulation Number 19 of 2016 as a derivative regulation. This regulation is a policy in order to implement provisions of Article 28 and Article 29 of the Finance Minister Regulation Number 148/PMK.05/2016. BIFZA implements it because Ministry of Finance institutionally has a higher hierarchy in terms of related authority to regulate amount of annual mandatory money tariff.

Second, timeframe consideration. Annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 is caused by timeframe consideration between old and new annual mandatory money tariff that has not changed for a long time. It has not changed for 16 years. So, according to BIFZA, the long-unchanged policy is irrelevant and it needs to update according to economic condition in Batam at that time. The relevant of annual mandatory money tariff change according to BIFZA is broadly shown by percentage increase in tariff that is housing by 151,7% to 1.787% range, commercial by 176,1% to 868,1% range, industrial by 183,1% to 1.062,4% range, tourism by 195% to 395,2% range, cultivation area and others by 617,3% to 840,5% range, and public facilities and others by 470% to 2.640,4% range.

Third, Tax Object Selling Value adjustment. Annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 is caused by Batam Tax Object Selling Value in 2016 adjustment which is regulated by Batam City Government through Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency of Batam City. Batam Tax Object Selling Value in 2016 refers to Batam City Regulation Number 10 of 2011. Between the old annual mandatory money tariff and Batam Tax Object Selling Value in 2016 show a high gap that is range of 1:2,5 to 1:33,2 comparisons to all subdistricts in Batam.

4. 2. Advantage and Disadvantage of Annual Mandatory Money Tariff Change

Phenomenon of Annual Mandatory Money Tariff Change in 2016 shows stakeholders who have competence in accordance with their interests about advantage and disadvantage which are obtained. Preference of each stakeholders was obtained from three choices that are between supporting, rejecting, or abstaining to respond it. And, description of political market was obtained in that is exchange aspect (*catallactics*) between supplier and demanders based on economical human aspect (*homo economicus*). Advantage and disadvantage of annual mandatory money tariff change based on preference and political market of stakeholders that are *first*, Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA). It is competent as the authority to determine annual mandatory money tariff. BIFZA has been preference to supporting annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are rejecting or abstaining. In political market, supporting to be a *catallactics* from BIFZA as a supplier to all demander which is based by *homo economicus*. It believes that the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 benefits all components of community in Batam by development effect, and no one sides is harmed.

Second, Community Organizations in Batam. It is competent as a presentation of interests from community and workers in Batam which related to annual mandatory money tariff. Community organizations in Batam have been preference to rejecting annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are supporting or abstaining. In political market, rejecting to be a *catallactics* from community organizations in Batam as a demander to BIFZA as a supplier which are based by *homo economicus*. It believes that the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 harms community and workers in Batam, and it actually benefits BIFZA.

Third, Businessman Organizations in Batam. It is competent as a presentation of interests from businessmen in Batam which related to annual mandatory money tariff. Businessman organizations in Batam have been preference to rejecting annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are supporting or abstaining. In political market, rejecting to be a *catallactics* from businessman organizations in Batam as a demander to BIFZA as a supplier which are based by *homo economicus*. It believes that the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 harms businessmen and community in Batam, and it actually benefits BIFZA.

Fourth, Regional House of Representatives of Batam City. It is competent as a aspirations receiver from all of community in Batam which related to annual mandatory money tariff. Regional House of Representatives of Batam City has been preference to rejecting annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are supporting or abstaining. In political market, rejecting to be a *catallactics* from Regional House of

Representatives of Batam City as a demander to BIFZA as a supplier which are based by *homo economicus*. It believes that the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 harms community in Batam, and it actually benefits Singapore and Malaysia.

Fifth, Batam City Government. It through Regional Tax and Retribution Management Agency of Batam City is competent as the authority to determine Batam Tax Object Selling Value in 2016 that is one of the main reason of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016. Batam City Government has been preference to abstaining which related to annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 rather than two other options that are supporting or rejecting. In political market, Batam City Government gives a solution that is Special Economic Zone to the annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016. Special Economic Zone provides new arrangement of distribution of land allocation services (specifically housing) between Batam City Government and BIFZA. This solution to be a *catallactics* from Batam City Government as a demander to BIFZA as a supplier which are based by *homo economicus*. It is abstaining (not to determine) because they are a fellow executive institution that is not supposed to conflict.

5. Closing

5.1. Conclusion

The conclusions of this research are:

- a. Three reasons of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 are unilateral action from Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority (BIFZA) as a Public Service Agency because it does not coordinate with community organizations in Batam, businessman organizations in Batam, Regional House of Representatives of Batam City, and Batam City Government which related to analysis of people purchasing power and economic conditions in Batam that based at Finance Minister Regulation Number 100/PMK.05/2016. Addition, in Tax Object Selling Value adjustment, coordination with Batam City Government was not carried out. Thus, the policy of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 caused controversy that is rejection from various sides, and it also disrupts economic activities in Batam because the determination was not included with clear guidelines.
- b. The advantage side of annual mandatory money tariff change in 2016 is BIFZA because it is the highest income (it recorded 400 billion (*rupiah*) revenue from all of total 986 billion (*rupiah*) revenue in 2015 [16]), and also foreign investors because annual mandatory money is not a burden for them but a burden for domestic investors so that the it does not contribute to reducing the gap between them (difference in investment value in Batam in 2016 is US \$ 392,19 million for foreign investment and 20,17 million US \$ for domestic investment [9 p55]). While, the disadvantage sides of annual mandatory money change in 2016 are community, businessmen, and workers because of limited purchasing power to people, high investment expense to businessmen, and triggered employment termination to workers.

5.2. Recommendation

The recommendations to Batam Indonesia Free Zone Authority are:

- a. Does not determine annual mandatory money tariff change unilaterally but by coordinating to ask for input that related to people purchasing power, Tax Object Selling Value adjustment, amount of tariff determination, economic conditions and others to community organizations in Batam, Businessman organizations in Batam, Regional House of Representatives of Batam City, and Batam City Government.
- b. Transparency related to all annual mandatory money tariff drafting processes that all sides can give input which based on their respective interests. So, a win-win solution can be achieved that is mutually benefit and not harm both sides.

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